

THE TRAGEDY OF THE OCEANS -- THE 1981 DEADLINE REVISITED

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ABSTRACT

The past year has seen a major shift with regard to federal ocean dumping policy. The Congressionally-mandated 1981 deadline on the ocean dumping of harmful sewage sludge and industrial wastes has not been implemented due to a Court order in response to a legal challenge to EPA's ocean dumping regulations. At the same time, a number of municipalities and advisory groups have been calling for greater use of the oceans as a waste disposal alternative. Congress, in reauthorizing Titles I & II of the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act of 1972 is presently considering a number of legal, public policy, and scientific issues relevant to the future use of the oceans to assimilate society's wastes. The authors review the current legislative proposals and summarize several policy options which have been proposed with regard to reauthorizing the Ocean Dumping Act.

INTRODUCTION

The passing of the 1981 deadline on the ocean dumping of harmful sewage sludge and industrial wastes has been a landmark event in the ongoing struggle to formulate a consistent national ocean dumping policy. The debate over the future use of the oceans to dispose of society's waste, which many thought was resolved in 1972 and then again in 1977, is just beginning anew and will likely remain unsettled until mankind learns how to solve the myriad of related waste disposal problems. Whether the oceans will be used as the ultimate sink for our nation's wastes remains for Congress to determine.

The critical need for a national policy regulating the ocean dumping of material harmful to the marine environment was first addressed in a 1970 Council on Environmental Quality Report entitled Ocean Dumping - A National Policy. Although the Report clearly recognized that the capacity of land-based disposal sites was quickly becoming exhausted in

some coastal areas and that communities would be increasingly looking to the oceans as a dumping ground for their wastes, the Council recommended that the ocean dumping of sewage sludge and other material harmful to the marine environment be phased out as soon as possible and no new sources allowed.

In response to the CEQ Report, Congress enacted the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act of 1972 specifically prohibiting the ocean dumping of radiological, chemical, or biological warfare agents or high-level radioactive wastes. Section 102 of the Act establishes a permit system regulating the ocean dumping of material found not to unreasonably degrade or endanger human health, welfare, or amenities, or the marine environment, ecological systems or ecological potentialities. The Act also requires the Administrator of EPA to establish and apply criteria for reviewing and evaluating permit applications and sets forth a number of criteria required to be considered. Most of the criteria established in the act address health and environmental impacts. The Administrator was also required, however, to determine the need for the proposed dumping and the probable impact of requiring the use of alternative locations or methods.

1981 OCEAN DUMPING DEADLINE

The 1977 Amendments to the Ocean Dumping Act specifically mandate the Administrator of EPA to end the dumping of sewage sludge into ocean waters as soon as possible and provide that "in no case may the Administrator issue any permit, or any renewal thereof which authorizes any such dumping after December 31, 1981." For the purposes of imposing the deadline, the term 'sewage sludge' was defined to mean "any solid, semisolid, or liquid waste generated by a municipal wastewater treatment plant, the ocean dumping of which may unreasonably degrade or endanger human health, welfare, amenities, or the marine environment, ecological systems, or economic

potentialities." 1980 Amendments expanded the Act to include the dumping of industrial wastes which resulted in unreasonable degradation and reaffirmed the deadline provision as on sewage sludge.

The Merchant Marine and Fisheries Committee Report clearly indicates that the Ocean Dumping Regulations and Criteria issued by EPA in 1977 were to be used in determining whether the ocean disposal of the sludge unreasonably degraded the marine environment and that the Committee was unhappy with EPA's progress in phasing out sludge dumping. According to the Committee's Report:

The Merchant Marine and Fisheries Committee has not been satisfied with EPA's progress in curbing harmful ocean dumping. In particular, the Committee is concerned with EPA's reluctance to establish firm phaseout dates for harmful ocean dumping and, more importantly, with EPA's continued sanctioning of the ocean dumping of materials -- such as sewage sludge -- which cannot meet EPA's own dumping criteria. In response to this concern, the Committee believes it is necessary to codify EPA's stated goal of ending ocean dumping of sewage sludge which is harmful to the marine environment or to human health, welfare, and amenities. Further, the Committee wants to terminate the ocean dumping of sewage sludge which may be harmful to the marine environment or to human health, welfare, and amenities. (1)

The 1981 deadline amendment passed the House of Representatives by a vote of 359 to 1 and was unanimously approved in the Senate.

"BALANCING OF ALTERNATIVES"

The extent to which the environmental impacts associated with land-based alternatives are required to be "balanced" by EPA in evaluating an ocean dumping permit request has been the subject of considerable controversy recently. New York City and several Northern New Jersey municipalities have challenged the Agency's regulations on the grounds that they failed to adequately address the environmental impacts associated with land-based disposal alternatives in determining whether ocean dumping "unreasonably degrades" the marine environment. In New York v. EPA, Federal Court Judge Abraham Sofaer interpreted the legislative history of the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuary Act to

require consideration of the environmental impacts associated with the alternatives to ocean dumping and held EPA's regulations invalid. (2)

The need to balance alternatives, however, was addressed and rejected by the Merchant Marine and Fisheries Committee in 1980 during consideration of legislation reauthorizing the Act. According to the Report language, the Committee considered an amendment to direct the Administrator of EPA to balance the impacts of ocean dumping sewage sludge against those of land disposal and select the least harmful alternative, thus allowing an extension of the 1981 deadline if ocean dumping were found to be least harmful. The amendment was defeated by a vote of 11 to 25. (3)

KEEPING THE OCEAN ALTERNATIVE OPEN

The passing of the 1981 deadline has generated considerable debate on the extent to which ocean dumping should continue to be considered as a waste disposal option. The debate has been intensified by the New York Court decision and the 1980 NACOA Report, The Role of the Oceans in a Waste Management Strategy, which calls for a rethinking of the special protective status given to the oceans.

Although the NACOA Report focused considerable attention on the limited disposal options available to municipalities and on the fragmented approach to air, land, and water protection measures, the Report failed to make any specific recommendations addressing the question of ocean dumping in the New York Bight Apex other than the need for additional monitoring, research and regional solutions.

The concern over the interrelationship between air, land, and water disposal options, however, is not new and has been addressed by a number of Advisory Committee and Government Accounting Office (GAO) Reports. Indeed, the 1969 Stratton Commission Report, Our Nation and the Sea, stressed the fact that waste disposal and pollution in the ocean and estuaries are often inseparable from pollution upstream and even pollution in the air and on land. The Report went on to say:

The oceans and marine-related activities must be viewed in the context of the total land-air-sea environment. In many ways, the oceans are the dominant factor in this total environment. However,

intervention by man in any one element produces effects on the others, frequently through processes we do not yet understand. Mankind is fast approaching a stage when the total planetary environment can be influenced, modified, and perhaps controlled by human activities. The Nation's stake in the oceans is therefore an important part of its stake in the very future of man's world. (4)

Even the 1970 CEQ Report which called for an end to the ocean dumping of sewage sludge and other material which unreasonably degraded the marine environment recognized that the alternatives to ocean dumping could also present some environmental problems, including the potential for groundwater contamination. CEQ also recognized that major political and financial barriers existed to acquiring new sites and disposal technologies.

Several GAO Reports issued since 1977 have also studied the "limited disposal options" and complexities resulting from separate legal and institutional frameworks protecting the air, land, and water environments as well as the impacts associated with alternatives to ocean dumping. Among other things, the GAO Reports have recommended increased consideration of the use of sludge on Agricultural lands and pretreatment as a means of improving sludge quality and providing more options for sludge disposal. The GAO has also favorably commented on the application of sludge to non-agricultural lands, pyrolysis, and the codisposal of sludge and solid wastes to produce energy as viable disposal alternatives. (5) The 1977 GAO Report, Problems and Progress in Regulating Ocean Dumping of Sewage Sludge and Industrial Wastes, stressed both the environmental harm associated with ocean dumping and as well as the potential detrimental impacts associated with the alternatives when viewed in terms of the total environment. (6)

THE NEW YORK AND PHILADELPHIA EXPERIENCES

Perhaps the major difficulty imposed on dumpers in seeking alternatives to marine disposal is financial. It is costly to remove heavy metals and persistent organics from wastes once these materials are commingled with large volumes of water and less noxious materials at a treatment plant collector site. Philadelphia, forced to discontinue ocean dumping by EPA, opted for point source control, putting the onus on industries to

pretreat effluents before discharging wastes into the city system. Partially due to the stringent enforcement actions taken by EPA Region III, Philadelphia has found alternatives other than ocean disposal for its sludges and currently recycles its waste as soil enrichment compost, strip mine revitalization compost and road repair solids. Composting and experimental forms of incineration are more costly than ocean dumping so a resurgence in the use of the ocean may well mean a return to the less costly approach even by cities on the threshold of constructive recycling. New York City and the other current sewage sludge dumpers are distinct from Philadelphia in that alternative waste treatment strategies were reviewed on paper and summarily rejected. These cities have made little effort to impose stringent controls on industries within their municipal boundaries to institute point source control. Obviously, strong regulatory control on waste input at the municipal level neither attracts business nor encourages existing industries to remain in a municipality subject to increased overhead.

Unfortunately, antiquated sewer systems are a major source of most of the heavy metal contamination. Little short of replacing the labyrinth of combined sewer overflows with non-leaching dually constructed systems will alleviate this aspect of the problem. Once again, cost is the primary factor controlling such decisions. Ideally, as portions of a system require repairs, a dual system should be installed. This solution has been given little consideration even when proposed in communities under less financial pressure than the City of New York. Unfortunately, industrial municipalities, in particular, are faced with difficult decisions; they may institute strong municipal waste control standards at a cost to industrial and residential users or challenge federal regulations mandated by a need for comprehensive environmental protection across state boundaries.

The paths taken by the cities of Philadelphia and New York City may be due partly to the very different implementation of regulations by EPA's region III and II, respectively. As mentioned previously, the Report language on the 1977 amendments indicated that Congress was losing confidence in EPA's ability to compel municipalities to halt the ocean dumping of harmful sewage sludge and other materials that failed to pass the Agency's ocean dumping criteria. EPA region II and its regulation of New York City's sewage dumping is evidence that Congressional loss of confidence was and still is justified.

Differences in implementation of the existing law are also apparent in the disparate approach to monitoring the impacts of sewage sludge dumping. Region II required the City of New York to supply data pertaining to water column parameters. Such data can inform scientists of impending anoxic conditions heralding possible fish kills, but such data provide little information on the other aspects of the ocean environment. Despite continued dumping of persistent heavy metals and toxic organics, Region II required no monitoring of body burdens of these materials in the benthos.

Region III, on the other hand, instituted its own monitoring program of Philadelphia's dumpsite and began by sampling for a multitude of parameters before settling on a more limited program adequate for an assessment of biological impacts. (7)

In defense of Region II, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) had an extensive study of the New York Bight ongoing since the early 1970's. Unfortunately, the benthic survey was on a gridwork design and, as such, was conducted to characterize the status of the New York Bight ecosystem, not to determine impacts or rates of degradation due to sewage sludge dumping for management purposes. (8) Much of the survey data is fraught with taxonomic inconsistencies, high inter-cruise, and inter-replicate variability, and serious deficiencies in the nature and reliability of sediment grain-size data. A design that better recognizes the heterogeneity of the study area would provide a more thorough understanding of the benthos-sediment interrelationships which are critical to the selection of human activities on Bight communities. (9)

OCEAN DUMPING ACT--NEEDED REFORMS?

In light of the growing controversy surrounding the use of the oceans as a waste disposal option and the failure of the EPA to enforce the 1981 ocean dumping deadline, substantive changes in the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuary Act may be necessary. The debate in the scientific community over the assimilative capacity of the oceans and whether the dumping of sludges, industrial wastes and even radioactive wastes constitutes "unreasonable degradation" can be expected to continue indefinitely. However, Congress will be expected to move forward with its review of the public policy considerations and take some definitive actions despite the scientific community's inability to reach a consen-

sus on how to best go about the task of disposing harmful materials with a minimum of environmental degradation. During the 97th Congress, a number of substantive amendments to the Ocean Dumping Act were proposed. Among other things, the one-year reauthorization legislation establishes a two-year moratorium on the ocean disposal of low-level radioactive wastes, directs the EPA to implement dumpsite designation and monitoring programs, and clarifies U.S. obligations to adhere to provisions of the London Ocean Dumping Convention binding on the United States. (10)

The Merchant Marine and Fisheries Committee has also devoted considerable attention to the New York Bight Apex and to its status as one of the most severely degraded open coastal areas in the world. The Committee's attention on the Bight Apex has been focused by continued sludge dumping at the 12-mile site and by the possibility that "fish kills" similar to the event that occurred in 1976 could happen again under certain conditions. Clearly, the Bight Apex area will continue to receive special attention as EPA reviews requests to redesignate the 12-mile site and as reports of serious water quality degradation and possible oxygen depletion events continue.

In the event EPA fails to foreclose the ocean dumping option at the 12-mile sludge site, Congress may be forced to do so legislatively. Indeed, during the recent reauthorization debate an amendment was offered to prohibit the dumping of any sewage sludge whatsoever in the Bight Apex. A similar amendment, closing the Bight Apex to sludge that failed to meet the environmental criteria set forth in the Act and requiring EPA to submit a legislative proposal containing additional measures necessary to achieve the long-term restoration of this badly polluted area was narrowly defeated during the Merchant Marine and Fishery Committee markup. Similar amendments can be expected to arise in the future.

MONITORING AND "UNREASONABLE DEGRADATION"

In approving an amendment adding a definition of "monitoring" to the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act, the Merchant Marine and Fisheries Committee has attempted to provide EPA with further guidelines for appropriate compliance and enforcement action. The definition provides maximum flexibility for the design of a monitoring effort suitable to the type of waste and to the designated site. In the design of an appropriate program, the regulator is provided with a series of five monitoring

parameters for consideration of applicability to the site-specific waste disposal need. Clearly, no program must by rote include all five parameters nor is the regulator limited to only those parameters cited but may employ any scientifically defensible program suited to the specific waste and site.

This provision ensures that in the event of increased ocean dumping, the impacts on the affected ocean communities, especially on the Outer Continental Shelf, will be considered in management decisions. The definition does not mandate specific instrumentation or procedures and as such is not limited by rapid progress being made in state of the art monitoring techniques. It does, however, impose upon the Agency the responsibility to consider more carefully ocean dumping monitoring needs with more discretion than has been shown in the past.

The need for adequate monitoring of expanded ocean dumping activity has been reemphasized by NACOA during both House and Senate hearings. The Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act delegates this responsibility to EPA but, to date, the Agency has demonstrated little management responsibility on a national level. In addition to a non-uniform interpretation of ocean dumping monitoring and regulatory requirements between coastal EPA Regions, the Agency has done little to provide centralized direction. The Act's reference to unreasonable degradation assumed that an Agency with marine scientific responsibility could develop a working definition of the term. In the decade since the Act has come into force, EPA has failed to develop adequate guidelines which quantify unreasonable degradation.

Until EPA publishes criteria for the interpretation of this much quoted term, the meaning of the language is literally in the mind of each affected party. In the New York Bight, studies have indicated that the benthic populations in a 240 square kilometer area surrounding the 12-mile sewage sludge dump site are decidedly altered. (11) To some, this rather large areal alteration of community structure might be considered unreasonable degradation. It has been noted that the alterations of macrobenthic community structure may have deleterious effects on demersal fishes and that species which tend to be disadvantaged are important prey species. (12). At what point can we quantify that community disruption or toxic accumulation is beyond the reasonable?

Do scientists have the capacity to determine when enough is enough? Does

the capacity exist in the regulatory realm to consider multiple sources of pollutant inputs whether they are classified as discharges, outfalls or dumps? Do legislative constraints and limited Committee jurisdictions prevent the development of adequate waste management strategies? For the moment, these questions remain unanswered.

At the same time, a number of scientists now claim that we can intensify the use of the oceans as a waste disposal option because we have not fully utilized the ocean's "assimilative capacity." But have we quantified this term adequately to understand how to use it? Consideration must be given to the limitations of the marine sciences to qualify and quantify not only the chemical and physical characteristics of ocean waters, but also their biological component. The NACOA document noted that "the biological availability of toxic materials in sediments at waste disposal sites is not easy to predict from knowledge of the chemical and biological processes occurring at the site." (13) The relationships of marine organisms within a community structure is only poorly understood in the best studied of marine sites. The biochemical and physiological capabilities of only a few marine organisms have been studied adequately to provide some insight into their ability to accommodate pollutant impacts. It's clear that further scientific study will be needed before these complex questions can be adequately answered.

PUBLIC POLICY CONSIDERATIONS

The controversial and complex debate over the future use of the oceans as a waste disposal option raises a number of important public policy questions. In light of the continuation of sewage sludge dumping beyond the 1981 deadline as well proposals to dispose low-level radioactive wastes in the sea, Congress must determine whether a major revision of the Marine Protection, Research, and Sanctuaries Act is necessary in order to formulate a clear and consistent federal policy with regard to ocean disposal. Both the volatility of the scientific debate concerning the assimilative capacity of the oceans and the public concern with the health of the marine environment justifies the close Congressional scrutiny. Further Congressional actions, however, will likely hinge on EPA's enforcement and site designation activities as well as how the Agency's new regulatory proposals are perceived.

Whether a major overhaul of the Ocean Dumping Act is necessary is not yet clear. Certainly, substantive amendments are likely to be offered and debated as dumping continues. Instituting an "ocean dumping user fee" and the creation of an "Ocean Waste Management Commission" to undertake a continuing review and assessment of research monitoring activities and needs, has received considerable attention in the 97th Congress. Regardless of whether or not sludge dumping is phased out in the near future or allowed to continue indefinitely, Congress must address the question of whether municipalities and industries should pay the "opportunity costs" for dumping in the oceans. An assessment based on the cost of environmentally acceptable land-based disposal alternatives could be used to fund the development of suitable alternatives as well as finance regional mitigation plans and compensate private citizens who may have been harmed as a result of continued dumping.

Other areas for possible amendments include imposing strict liability standards on ocean dumpers for harm directly attributable to their contribution of pollutants to the marine environment and establishing a higher degree of protection for sensitive coastal or "pristine" areas where the impact of ocean dumping cannot be predicted with certainty. At the same time, regional strategies for waste management as well as regional mitigation plans to clean up already severely degraded areas such as the N.Y. Bight Apex must be developed. Issues related to future research and monitoring needs, as well as "baseline" monitoring projects must also be addressed.

Certainly, the most important public policy question which Congress needs to address in the near future is whether the oceans deserve some degree of special protection. The NACOA Report criticized Congress' fragmented approach to the protection of the nation's air, land and water but did not focus on the factors which make an individual assessment of each of these environments necessary. It is also clear that the same arguments which have been used to justify the continued ocean dumping of sewage sludge will be made in the near future to pry open the ocean alternative for the disposal of radioactive wastes and other hazardous materials which society is either unable or unwilling to dispose of in an environmentally acceptable manner.

Concern for the nation's groundwater supplies and inland water systems will continue to grow as science learns more about the the migration of dangerous

materials in these environments. At times, the immediate effect upon human health from current ocean disposal practices seems remote. But are we really faced with an either/or situation? Material disposed of in the ocean is unconfined and any effects may be difficult to statistically demonstrate given short-term and areally-limited monitoring efforts. An unknown must necessarily accompany such a waste disposal approach. Properly handled, sewage sludge and industrial wastes can be neutralized, recycled or contained, posing limited threat to groundwater systems. Land containment can be readily monitored. Expense separates the choices. Current awareness would force more careful monitoring on land. The oceans are costly to properly monitor as indicated by the paucity of broad-scale federal coastal monitoring efforts. The solution to this dilemma is fiscal, though these are not the times to be calling for costly solutions to problems many wish to ignore.

The extent to which the oceans will become the ultimate dumping ground for society's waste remains to be determined. The issue will likely remain unresolved until mankind learns how to solve a myriad of complex and interrelated waste disposal problems. The future of the oceans, though, will continue to remain for man to determine. Hopefully, we will have the foresight to make wise decisions and the will to carry them out.

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